

CRIMINAL JUSTICE IN KASHMIR: PRIMITIVISM TO MODERNISM**Sajad Ahmad Rather**

Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of History, University of Kashmir

Email Id: sajadhistory90@gmail.com**Abstract**

Kashmir has had been recognised as the exception in the entire sub-continent for having authentic literary tradition which other areas are lacking. This paper provides initially a brief political history with the glimpse of both indigenous and British laws and regulations prior to the codification of the laws. The main focus of this paper is on the process of flexibility of the criminal justice system in the pre-colonial period. It tries to show how these different legal systems were in practice, equally plural and made up of multiple layers of rules and authorities—the dharmadhkari, the qazi and the judge.

Introduction

Kashmir has been mentioned by Walter Lawrence as the land without crime.¹ This can be judged from the fact that state since ancient times maintained its legal system in a very appropriate manner. People were asked to follow the laws and rules breakdown of which a severe kind of punishment was given. Punishments are conferred not because of the fact that it has to be an eye for an eye or a tooth for a tooth, rather having its due impact on the society; while undue harshness is not required but inadequate punishment may lead to sufferance of the community at large.²

Justice United with Administration: Ancient Kashmir

In a broader sense crime can be defined as the violation of rules and regulations which are enforced both by the State and Society. The members of each and every society are expected to act in accordance with its established norms and law. Maladjustment of individuals essentially leads to breach of the norm. But there is no denying the fact that crime, however, is a relative term and is considered a crime by a particular society may not be so to another.³

Unfortunately there is dearth of sources or material on the administration of justice in ancient Kashmir. Most the earliest works like Rajatarangini (literally ‘River of Kings’ of Kalhana, Kuttanimata Kanya by Damodaragupta, Desopadesa- Narmamala, Samayamatrika and Dasavatracharita of Ksemendra and Dvitiyarajatarangini of Jonaraja provides scant picture of the judicial system of ancient Kashmir. There is no doubt that a close study of these sources helps us in framing the judicial administration up to the beginning of the Muslim rule in Kashmir.

As regards the question whether the Hindu criminal law was ever applied in practice, there seems to be hardly any reason to doubt that it was not. In this connection the regional texts like Nilamata

¹ Walter Lawrence, *The Valley of Kashmir*, (Mirpur: Chinar Publishing House, 1992), p. 37.

² *Jai Kumar vs. State of MP (1999) 5 Supreme Court Cases 1*

³ Sukla Das, *Crime and Punishment in Ancient India*, (New Delhi: Abhinav Publications, 1977), p. 13.

Purana, Rajatarangini of Kalhana, and works of Ksemendra, Somadeva and even earlier works like Kuttanimata-Kanya of Damodaragupta, clearly indicates that ancient law was applied and honoured by the kings of Kashmir. The famous author Kalhana's Rajatarangini contains ample references to crime and punishment which gives an insight in to the social degeneration in ancient Kashmir.⁴

The Nilamata Purana explicitly provides a valuable insight into the legal system of ancient Kashmir. It states that 'all people should be penalised in accordance with their crimes; the king should neither be very hard in giving punishments nor should forgive anyone and he must carry on administration in accordance with the instructions of the treatise on polity'.⁵ In the same tune Kalhana advocates the punishment on the basis of specifications of a particular situation as well as at appropriate scale.⁶ Further advice shows the intellect of the author ahead of the times when he advises the king that he in no case should harm the sons, wives, friends and relatives of the guilty person whom he punished for the criminality. There is no exaggeration in saying that the concept of separation of the crime from the criminal was wholly in tune with the Hindu philosophy and appears to have been well prevalent in ancient Kashmir. Having fully considered the time and the place (of the crime), the strength and the knowledge (of the offender), the king had to justly inflict the punishment on those who acted unjustly. Unlike in ancient India, the death penalty was used very often in number of the cases like treason, embezzlement of State funds and theft as well.⁷ Unfortunately there was no rule of law as the punishment was awarded and governed by the considerations of status of the accused. Caste status essentially contributed to determining the seriousness of the offence. In other words, the general principles adopted was that rights, duties and liabilities varied with caste or sex and thus punishments and damages were determined by the [status] of the accused or defendant and that of the complaint and plaintiff. Naturally Brahmans were the most privileged class and came to occupy the key positions within the society in general and the criminal justice system in particular. The law gives prescribe that a Brahman was not to be sentenced to death or corporal punishment for any offence what so ever, but if they were guilty of an offence deserving the death penalty, Brahman was to be punished by his entire head shaved, he also might be banished from the country, a mark appropriate to the grave sin committed by him might be branded on his forehead and he might be paraded on an ass.⁸

⁴ There were numerous crimes prevalent in the society during ancient Kashmir including treason, embezzlement of State funds, kidnapping of women, adultery and forging of State documents. The punishment too varied according to the degree of crime and caste-- death-sentence, confiscation of wealth, deputation to unknown places, amputation of body organs and various types of shamming.

⁵ Ved Kumari, tr. *Nilamata Purana*, vol.ii, (Srinagar: J&K Academy of Art, Culture and Languages, 1973), pp. 72-73.

⁶ Kalhana states that the wise-men valued highly the quick punishments which the king named Uccala of mighty glory meted out to the cruel *Kayasthas* (official class). Because those who know the wise use of punishment of low bred horses, *Kayasthas*, persons possessed by goblins and enemies. For if they are not punished at the proper time they can pose a great threat to the king. For further details see Rajatarangini, VIII, 113-115.

⁷ M.A. Stein, tr. Kalhana's *Rajatarangini*, vol. VIII, (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1989), P. 186.

⁸ Gout. XII, 43; see also Manu, VIII, 123, 380-81; one of the indigenous punishments that both Indian Penal Code and Ranbir Penal Code did away with was the public display of a criminal on the back of an ass. Lord Macaulay perceived this as a parallel to the English pillory.

It is true that in ancient Kashmir the caste system had not attained full rigidity but still Brahman's were the most privileged class. The Kalhana's *Rajatarangini* refers to a case in the reign of king Chandrapida of Kashmir (A.D.713-721) when a Brahman guilty of murder of a Brahman was exempted from death sentence because of the prevalence of a Smriti rule. Kalhana expresses the view that 'none is to be punished till the charge is established and that a Brahman even if proved guilty is exempted from capital punishment'.⁹ All this shows that according to the penal code of Manusmriti, for the punishment to be proportionate to the pollution incurred.

Another interesting feature of the punishments was that a Brahman could either be banished, or humiliated, in accordance with law prevalent and sometimes branded with a dog's feet on his forehead or even could be fined.¹⁰

In the absence of any codified law, there are certain instances where the kings of Kashmir during ancient times punished the guilty man at their own will. It was contradictory with the law that Brahmins enjoyed the privilege of not being killed. In *Rajatarangini* we have several references where the Brahmins were executed by the [so] called naughty tyrants and rebels. Besides, kings at times allowed them to die through Prayopavesa.¹¹ It is interesting to note that during the reign of Jayapida (A.D.753-782) because of the Brahmins opposition to stop fiscal oppression, most of them preferred to leave the country. And those who resisted were either imprisoned or executed and even left to bear numerous hardships. Their lands were confiscated and the king himself declared/ announced that "let it to be reported to me if a hundred Brahmins less than one die in a single day." In a similar vein, during the reign of king Harsha (A.D.1089-1101), Kalhana refers that when furious Damaras¹² fully utilized/ exploited the anarchical condition and had become ever powerful, he took many serious steps to suppress or crush them. Further it is worthwhile to note, says Kalhana while he (king) was killing the Lavanyas,¹³ he left in Madavarajya not even a single Brahmin alive if he wore his hair dressed high and was of prominent appearance.

Essentially it shows that the sovereignty of the State lies in the king, who is of divine origin and had absolute power; also it is true that the legal system was not uniform or codified, but was moulded according to the contemporary needs and aspirations. In actuality, the administration of justice in ancient Kashmir was the duty of the king (or similar personages) and its practice was elucidated and elaborated by the idea of dharma. Nothing like modern legislation or a written code of laws existed during ancient Kashmir.¹⁴ The king himself constituted the law-making agency. The *Rajatarangini* refers to the king's seat of judgement as dharmasana,¹⁵ surrounded by the

⁹ Stein, Kalhana's *Rajatarangini*, IV, pp. 96-106.

¹⁰ Ibid, p. 109.

¹¹ In context of ancient Kashmir, it means solemn fasts or voluntary starvation.

¹² *Damaras* were a class of hereditary and feudal landholders that played a crucial part in the politics of Kashmir during eleventh and twelfth centuries.

¹³ It is name of the one of the ruling tribes in ancient Kashmir who had been the constant source of menace to both people and the king.

¹⁴ The basis of the justice seems to have been sacred books as well as tradition.

¹⁵ V.N.Drabu, *Kashmir Polity C 600-1200 A.D.*, (New Delhi: Bahri Publications Private Limited, 1986), p. 179.

learned sabhyas.¹⁶ Similarly the court building is mentioned as adhikaranamandapa or asthanamandapa.¹⁷ True king's court was the highest court and the highest officer after king was the rajasthana or dharmadikara (chief-justice). Below him, there were other judges are denoted by the terms like tantapati, rajagrhyas etc.

There was no distinction between civil and criminal court and the same court tried both civil and criminal cases. The laws and the judicial system were not much caste bound, though Brahmins enjoyed many privileges including the exemption from taxation and capital punishments. The Nilamata Purana makes it clear that a king should neither be very harsh in awarding punishments nor should be condone the offence of the culprit. The king as an epitome of judiciary should execute the sentence in accordance with the principles laid down in the rajasastras (treatise on polity).¹⁸

The punishments included death sentence,¹⁹ confiscation of property or wealth, deportation to unknown places²⁰ and amputation of various body organs.²¹ Various forms of shaming were main form of punishment. The concluding Tarangas (lit. waves: books in context of the text) of the Rajatarangini contains many references of the culprits and suspected criminals being executed on the pale or by rope down round the neck during night. Author cum philosopher Ksemendra also refers to the hanging of criminals fixed on the stake. All this suggests that the penal code was quite severe in ancient Kashmir. But it is equally important to mention the Hindu rule continued up to the 13th century speaks high about the working and efficiency of the judicial system of the region.

Justice, State and Contemporary Time: Medieval Kashmir

The year 1339 A.D marks an important landmark in the history of the Kashmir. It was in that year Sultan Shams-ud-Din Shahmir (1339-1342) laid the foundation of the Muslim rule which lasted for more than four centuries. The advent of the Muslim rule clearly led to the application of the Muslim law in Kashmir and the emergence of new and distinct forms of laws and judicial institutions were the bi-products of this political change. It was Sultan Shahmir who first introduced Muslim law in Kashmir and made it the law of the land. The Hindu laws, customs and usages, which were applicable before his reign, were repealed by the traditional Muslim law.²² The Syed's²³ who migrated to the valley played an important role for the implementation of the Muslim law. It is pertinent to mention that the establishment of the Muslim rule had practically paved the

¹⁶ Judges, Councillors or jurors

¹⁷ V.N. Drabu, *Kashmir Polity*, p. 179

¹⁸ Ved Kumari, *Nilamata Purana*, p.221

¹⁹ Treason, embezzlement of the State funds and kidnaping of women were the crimes in which the death sentence was mostly followed.

²⁰ Adultery

²¹ Forging of the State documents

²² Hakim Imtiyaz Hussain, *Muslim Law and Customs*, (Kashmir: Srinagar Law Journal Publication, 1989), p. 95

²³ It was on the advice of a great missionary, Mir Syed Ali Hamadani, Sultan Qutb-ud-Din divorced one of his wives, who were real sisters to each other; marriage with two women who are real sisters to each other is not permitted by Islam.

way for the introduction of Islamic institutions like Shaikh-ul-Islam, Qazi, Mufti, Mir adl, Mohtasib and the like.

The government of the Sultan's of Kashmir, as elsewhere in rest of India, was an absolute monarchy in both legal and political terms. As noted, in the sultanate administration, the king was the highest judicial authority and the fountain head of justice. As such the king's court was the highest court of appeal which tried cases of rebellion and civil and criminal suits. It was both the court of first instance and a court of appeal. The justice was dispensed with by the Sultan sitting in the Diwan-Khana in the open durbar every day.²⁴ Unlike the Ottoman Empire, the Sultan was an "absolute monarch" in whose person "were fused the threefold functions of government, legislative executive and judicial, he was the pivot upon which turned the entire machinery of public life."²⁵ Compared to Ottomans, where the Shaikh ul-Islam could theoretically remove the Sultan for violating the Holy Law, the Sultan faced no immediate institutional checks to his rule. The Sultanate monarchs used punishments that ranged from harsh to milder including flogging, qisas, tashir,²⁶ amputation of body organs and gouging out the eyes by needle. It seems true that the purpose of these brutal punishments was ebrat (example). We find the significant contrast to the contemporary practices of punishments during the Sultan Zain-ul- Abidin's (1420-1470) reign. The Sultan was opposed to the infliction of harsh and brutal punishments upon the offenders against law. For ordinary offences he professed to give milder punishments. Thus, he decreed that the thieves and robbers should not be executed, nor even be flogged, but were arrested and put in chains to work on land and public buildings to earn their livelihood by hard work.²⁷ It was in this context the Sultan was ahead of his times and was definitely one of glaring example of the reformation of the offender.

The sultanate period displayed many of the features of the curious mixture of the patrimonial and medieval states. Though the state was weak, there were no substantive legal restraints on the rule of the Sultan. The normative frame work of the Sharia and the circle of justice was an important factor in measuring the legitimacy of the rulers in the eyes of the people but did not generate any institutional or legal checks on the command of the Sultan, which was in practice, arbitrary and all powerful. The laws generally applied were that of Hanafi law among the Sunnis and the Shia law among the Shias. There are only few indirect references to the procedure and evidences which governed the Sultans court; as regards to other courts nothing is clearly known. Also there were no lawyers to assist the litigants. Consequently there was the absence of uniformity and unanimity in the judicial administration.

The Mughal period that lasted from 1586-1753, marks one of the significant phases in the history of Kashmir, the status of Kashmir as a sovereign country came to an end on 6th October, 1586, when after the third attempt, the Mughals entered Srinagar in trump and Kashmir was made part of the province of Kabul. For the administrative convenience the Subah of the Kabul was

²⁴ Mohibbul Hasan, *Kashmir Under the Sultans*, (Calcutta: Iran Society, 1959), p. 200

²⁵ N.K. Zutshi, *Sultan Zain-ul-Abidin of Kashmir*, (Srinagar: Gulshan Books,2012), p. 95

²⁶ Public humiliation during the Zain ul Abiden's reign for murder

²⁷ Mohibbul Hasan, *Kashmir Under the Sultans*, p. 84

subdivided into seven Sarkars: Kashmir, Pakli, Bimbar, Swat, Bajaur, Kandahar and Zubulistan.²⁸ Acting on the advice of Akbar, Qasim Khan, after conquering Kashmir, embarked on the project of manufacturing consent and consolidating the imperial control. Abu Fazl makes causal reference in the following words, “the ignorant [wild] people of Kashmir were pacified by the administration of justice and by the increase of love”. Throughout the whole period the internal affairs of the Subah of Kashmir were administered by a Subadar whom the imperial authority appointed.²⁹ In the same tune the administration of justice was wholly in the hands of Subadar (governor) who worked on the behalf of the emperor as the supreme judicial authority in his respective Subah. He delegated these functions to the Mansabdar of each Sarkar (district) and Pargana. Kashmiri’s were, however, fortunate in being able to present their disputes and complaints to the emperor personally when they visited valley on holiday.³⁰ This proved an effective check on the authority of the governor and the subordinate staff as well.³¹

As noted, the Subadar was vice-regent of the emperor³² and carried on the administration of the Subah on his behalf in accordance with the rules and regulations set forth from time to time. His appointment was made under an imperial Farman called Farmani Sabti, in which the directives and guidelines were laid down.³³ He held regular courts and discharged important judicial functions.³⁴ Criminal as well as civil cases of complicated nature were essentially lodged in his court.

Evidently Mughals applied Muslim Law in the Suba of Kashmir in the same way as being applied in rest of the country and for that purpose the officials were appointed.³⁵ In Islamic Jurisprudence, the central aim of upholding the law was to maintain justice (adala). In the political or administrative realm, it was meant applying the holy law and achieving a balance (al-mizan) between the rights and obligations of the rulers and the ruled. There was no uniformity in the punishments during the Mughal period and these ranges from harsher to milder. Death penalty could be inflicted by hanging, beheading and impaling, also various forms of execution were prevalent.³⁶ The other common forms of punishment were mutilation, flogging, banishment, imprisonment, fines and confiscations, forfeiture of rank and title, forbidding the court and dismissals. In sum the ruler, the judicial officials, the Subedars, the Kotwals and others evaluated the gravity of the offences and penalized the offender accordingly. Evidently, the Mughal period too was characterised by the legal pluralism in the strict sense of the term.

About the middle of the eighteenth century Kashmir passed into the hands of the rulers of

²⁸ Abul Fazl, *The Ain I Akbari*, tr. C H S Jarrett, vol.ii (Calcutta: Asiatic Society of Bengal, 1891), p. 347

²⁹ James P. Ferguson, *Kashmir: An Historical Introduction*, (Srinagar: Gulshan Books, 2009), p. 135

³⁰ Akbar visited Kashmir three times, Jahangir five times, Shahjahan four times and Aurangzeb once.

³¹ P N K Bamzai, *Culture and Political History of Kashmir*, vol.ii (Srinagar: Gulshan Publications, 2015), p.202

³² Abul Fazl, *Ain I Akbari*, vol. II pp. 223-25

³³ P. Saran, *The Provincial Government of the Mughals 1526-1658*, (Allahabad: Kitabistan, 1941), p. 176

³⁴ P. Saran, *The Provincial Government of the Mughals*, p. 185

³⁵ Imtiyaz Hussain, *Muslim Law and Customs*, p. 98

³⁶ The various executions are throwing a man down from the roof, to get criminals trampled under the feet of elephant, stung to death by snakes, torn to pieces by dogs.

Kabul, and the times of the “Shahani Durani” are still remembered with a shudder.³⁷ For 66 years (1753-1819) Kashmir remained under the rule of five Afghan kings and like Mughals they also sent their governors to Kashmir to rule for them. It is fact that in total twenty eight (28) Afghan governors and deputy-governors, directly or indirectly ruled over Kashmir.³⁸

In Kashmiri language, there is a phrase--- Koali Khote Koal Sardie, which means ‘a man, while wandering in search of a hot stream, finds only a cold stream’. He proceeds further in the hope of finding a warm stream only to find the next one colder than the one he left. The people of Kashmir thought that with the ushering in of the Afghan rule, their problems would be over but the new rule brought more miseries and sufferings. Under the Afghans the Kashmir was no better than under the Mughals. In fact, it was worse as Kashmir passed through a regime of oppression and tyranny. The Pathan rulers are now only remembered for their brutality and cruelty, and it is said of the Afghans that they thought no more of cutting off heads than of plucking a flowers³⁹

‘sir buridan pesh in sangin dilan gulchidan ast’

Almost all subedars sent from Kabul were much affected by pleasure and enjoyment in the country that they tried to become independent. As long as the kingdom of Kabul wielded some sceptre of authority and the country was not distracted by civil wars, the Durrani kings sent expeditions to Kashmir from time to time which brought upheavals in their train and some semblance of law and order was maintained. When the factious war began at Kabul and Mohammad Shah captured Zaman Shah, the conditions worsened at home. Naturally, the royal hold on Kashmir was relaxed and even the outward show of peace vanished.⁴⁰

This shows the total disconnect from the centre and also speaks volumes about their personality and fragile commitment. The lust for wealth, power and authority marked the chief features of Afghan governance in Kashmir. The political conditions did not permit them to introduce changes in the judicial and administrative system of Kashmir. Thus, the Muslim law, as was being applied in the valley during the Mughals, continued to remain in force.

The Afghan were seldom known for their sense of justice. They only knew how to torture and fleece people.⁴¹ The question of dispensing any justice by some judicial authority never arouse during the Afghan time.⁴² So, there was nothing commendable about the law and order in Kashmir during the Pathan rule. There was no special court to administer justice. Neither there was any code of procedure, nor any trained person to administer justice impartially. This aphorism speaks the sorry state of criminal justice system of Pathans in Kashmir:

Tetis Laras Zan Tulnas Kalah (speedy punishment)

[He was beheaded like the bitter end of a cucumber].

The Pathan rulers were famed for their quick justice (very often injustice). No sooner was

³⁷ W.R Lawrence, *The India We Served*, (London: Cassell and Company Ltd., 1928), p. 124

³⁸ Mohammad Saleem Khan, *The History of Medieval Kashmir*, (Srinagar: Gulshan Books, 2006), p. 160

³⁹ G.M.D. Sufi, *Kashir: Being a History of Kashmir*, (New Delhi: Capital Publishing House, reprint 1996), p.676.

⁴⁰ M. Aslam Khan, *Martial Spirit of Kashmiris*, (Srinagar: A.S. College Research Publication, 1981), p. 47

⁴¹ George forester, an Englishman, travelled to Kashmir in 1783 and described the sorry state of the Valley under Afghan rule---the cruelty, the execution and persecution.

⁴² Prithvi Nath Tikoo, *Story of Kashmir*, (New Delhi: Light and Light Publishers, 1989),p. 234

the order given “Behead the man,” or “Take out his eyes,” or “Cut off his nose,” then the executioner left and did this cruel deed.⁴³ With this ended one of the be-boj waqts (lawless and order less periods) in the history of Kashmir.

After more than sixty years of Afghan rule Kashmir once again changed hands, this time became part of the Sikh empire of the Maharaja Ranjit Singh of Punjab. It is interesting to note that the judicial system of the Ranjit Singh is said to be a fusion of the Mughal and Misaldari systems with some elements of the British Indian system. In the Sikh administration, the Maharaja was the highest judicial authority and the fountain-head of justice. The Maharaja decided all types of cases--civil and criminal, original and appellate. No matter was too small or too great to be brought before the personal attention of the Maharaja; sometimes even conjugal conflicts were decided by him.⁴⁴ In addition to this if the aggrieved person wants to seek justice from the Maharaja that he would appear in the public Darbar and shouted ‘dohai, maharaja dohai (mercy Maharaja mercy). The Maharaja after listening to his complaint took instant action to redress his grievance.

Nothing like modern legislation or a written code of laws existed during the Ranjit Singh’s reign. According to Steinbach ‘custom and caprice are substituted for the lex scripta’.⁴⁵ However, Muslim (shariat) law was applied by the Qazis in deciding cases of the Muslims and Shastras for the Hindus. All other cases civil or criminal were decided by a well-regulated customs and conventions.

There was non-existence of capital punishment for any crime whatsoever. Ranjit Singh never inflicted death sentence even when an attempt was made to assassinate him.⁴⁶ Fine and mutilation were the most important forms of punishments. Mutilation was reserved for such offences as violent theft, robbery, adultery and seduction.⁴⁷ Culprits were deprived of their arms, noses, ears or legs according to the degree of offence.⁴⁸ Fine was another important form of punishment awarded to both civil and criminal offences? At the same time it was imposed in place of corporal punishment. Impunity of all crimes from larceny to murder could be purchased by the payment of fine.⁴⁹ “A tolerable bag full of rupees is often accepted as compensation in full for the retention of a limb or feature.”⁵⁰ Thus, the administration of justice was a source of considerable income to the state. The other forms of punishment included imprisonment and confiscation of property,⁵¹ flogging, reprimand or rebuke by the Maharaja , inflicting wound on the forehead by a piece of

⁴³ J. Hinton Knowles, *A Dictionary of Kashmiri Proverbs and Sayings*, (Bombay: Education Society’s Press, 1885) p. 214

⁴⁴ K.K.Khullar, *Maharaja Ranjit Singh*, (New Delhi: Hem Publishers Pvt. Ltd., 1980), p. 173.

⁴⁵ Henry Steinbach, *The Punjab: Being a Brief Account of the Country of the Sikhs*, (London: Smith, Elder and Co. 1845), p. 71.

⁴⁶ W. G. Osborne, *The Court and Camp of Runjeet Sing*, (London: Henry Colburn Publisher, 1840), p.36

⁴⁷ Punjab Administrative Report, pp 10-11.

⁴⁸ W.G. Osborne, *The Court and Camp of Runjeet Sing*, p.55

⁴⁹ Punjab Administrative Report (P.A.R), pp. 10-11

⁵⁰ Henry Steinbach, *The Punjab: Being a Brief Account of the Country of the Sikhs*, P. 72.

⁵¹ These were awarded to those officials who were found guilty of embezzlement of revenue or any form of bribery.

hot iron, fancy punishment,⁵² ordeal of hot water for judging innocence or guilt of suspected offender, etc. The form of punishment was imprisonment; mutilation, so frequently practised by the Afghans being rarely resorted to. “On the branches of it (a Chinar tree), “writes Hugel, “criminals are hanged, a punishment of constant occurrence under the Pathan sway, when the smallest offence was visited by death, but now inflicted only in cases of murder. Men are too valuable to the present ruler to be lightly spared; penalties and stripes are, therefore, the usual punishment.⁵³ The people seem contented with the justice dealt out to them, and admitted to me that not more than one guilty person in every [twenty] is ever visited with the reward due to his crimes.” On the other hand, “the dreadful cruelties perpetrated by their earlier rulers (Afghans) who, for smallest offence, punished them with the loss of their body parts including noses or ears, make the poor Kashmiris well satisfied with their present comparatively mild government; and, in truth, there is very little oppression on the part of the Governors or Thanedars”.⁵⁴ This period too perpetuated oppression on the natives and is generally believed that Kashmir under Sikhs was “occupied” rather than governed.

The Period of Transition: Modern Kashmir

The Treaty by which Kashmir was transferred to the new Maharaja [Gulab Singh] became famous by the name of bi- nama-i Amritsar (Treaty of Amritsar). This Treaty marks the end of the Sikh rule in Kashmir as well as the foundation of the state of the Jammu and Kashmir.⁵⁵ In return for this important transaction, the Maharaja was to pay 75 lakhs of rupees to British government.⁵⁶

This treaty made the formal inauguration of the indirect rule in the state of Jammu and Kashmir and thus the uncertain and ambiguous process i.e. British Paramountcy and Internal Sovereignty was its immediate as well as long term consequence.

Though, Kashmir was ruled by the foreigners from centuries, together, however, the Dogras rule was unique in the sense that they were themselves the vassals of the another mightier power i.e. British colonialists.⁵⁷ From 1846, the princely state of Jammu and Kashmir witnessed new and unique political, administrative and socio-economic order. It is generally believed that Dogras inherited a system of justice which was medieval, insufficient and arbitrary. It is well known that the rule of law and justice was virtually unknown to the people as both Afghans and Sikhs were apathetic towards judicial administration. Further there was no special court to administer justice. Neither there was any code of procedure, nor any trained person to preside over law courts. At that time “to administer justice was the duty of no one, yet everyone, who held any

⁵² The face of culprit was blackened and he was made to sit on a donkey with a face towards the back of the animal and was paraded in the streets of town or village.

⁵³ Charles Baron Hugel *Travels in Kashmir and the Punjab*, (London: John Petheran, 1845), pp 128-29

⁵⁴ Charles Baron Hugel, *Travels in Kashmir and the Punjab*, p.156

⁵⁵ It was the beginning of the Dogra rule in the state which lasted from 1847-1947, marking Kashmiri’s transition to modern times.

⁵⁶ C. U. Aitchison, *A Collection of Treaties, Engagements and Sanads*, vol. ix, (Calcutta: Foreign Office Press, 1892), p. 342.

⁵⁷ Altaf Hussain Para, *The Making of Modern Kashmir*, (London: Routledge, 2019), p. 12.

responsible post throughout the state, was responsible to administer it both in the civil and criminal cases”.⁵⁸

With the treaty of Amritsar, the state witnessed the emergence of absolute monarchical rule with the power mostly concentrated in one person – the Maharaja. The Dogras believed in the “divine right theory” of kingship and always concentrated all the judicial powers in their hands. The Maharaja himself constituted the law making agency, the chief executive and the highest tribunal of justice.⁵⁹ In the absence of any formal law or constitution, all that Maharaja willed became law and all that he prohibited became crime or sedition.

It is important to mention that at that time justice was that “those who could pay could at any time get out of jail, while the poor lived and died there almost without hope”.⁶⁰ It was during Maharaja Gulab Singh’s reign that the judicial system of the princely state of Jammu and Kashmir received its first footing and patronage, although there was practically no change in the then existing judicial administration. Sovereignty was parcellized to the governors and other officials⁶¹ who oversaw the judicial administration in their respective areas, served as the lowest courts with no written law.

Though the Maharaja was considered to be the law-making agency, but the prevailing customary law and legal practices were followed and in addition to the common sense, there were the Hindu and Muhammadan laws and the orders of the Maharaja which was called the “law of equity”. There was no law of limitation in force in the whole state.⁶² There were no legal advisors, and the officials were not required to record statements and judgements; cases were usually lodged, committed, represented and decided verbally.⁶³

The punishments for crimes were quite severe and maharaja’s methods of punishment were considered both primitive⁶⁴ and barbarous.⁶⁵ The rigorous punishments like torture, burning one alive in hay, drowning, breaking ones bones and death sentence were commonly practised.⁶⁶ The culprit for killing a cow (gau), was first boiled in hot oil(death penalty) but subsequently reduced to life imprisonment and finally to seven years of rigorous punishment. ⁶⁷ For the guilty of the murder (qatl) the punishment was Azhab which meant amputation of limbs before hanging one to death.⁶⁸

⁵⁸ Pandit Salig Ram Kaul, *The Biography of Maharaja Gulab Singh* (Srinagar: Salig Ram Press, 1923), p.237

⁵⁹ Gazi Ghulam Mohi uddin, *Development of Legislature in Jammu and Kashmir*,(Srinagar: Type- Script in the History Department Library, Kashmir university 1970), p. 1

⁶⁰ Francis. Younghusband, *Kashmir*, (London: Adam and Charles Black, 1911), p. 73

⁶¹ Kotwal, *Thanedar, Kardar, Zaildar, and Muqaddam*

⁶² Salig Ram Koul , *The Biography of Maharaja Gulab Singh*, p 237

⁶³ Salig Ram Koul, *The Biography of Maharaja Gulab Singh*, pp. 237-238

⁶⁴ Praveena Akhter Pandit, *Peasantry and the Agrarian System in Kashmir*,(Srinagar: City Book Centre, 2018), p.

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⁶⁵ W.R. Lawrence, *The India We Served*, p. 125

⁶⁶ Mirza Saif u din, *Roznamcha*, vol. ii, as cited in Praveena Akhter Pandit, p. 36

⁶⁷ *Hathai* a generic term used to convey for an unpardonable offence. See also, Biscoe, p. 123; M. Y. Ganai, pp.15-

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⁶⁸ S.N. Gadru, ed. *Kashmir Papers: British Intervention in Kashmir*,(Srinagar: Freethought Literature,1973), p. ix

Interestingly, it is pertinent to mention that during this period the incidence of crimes was low and some contemporary sources even speaks the total absence of crimes. It may be most probably due to the following reasons, the stern measures of repression adopted by Maharaja Gulab Singh. The flaying alive of thieves had its effect as a deterrent, and at present time the only criminals of the valley are the Galwans.⁶⁹ In addition to this the services and duties of the village headmen and watchmen were real and they receive small mercy if they fail to report crime or to detect the criminals;⁷⁰ and further the old system of informers have made criminal pursuits unpopular and unprofitable. It may be truly said that people are afraid to commit crimes Doosan Manz Chi Gagad.

The period from 1856 onwards is considered as a transitional period in the judicial history of the state. It was during Ranbir Singh's period that colonial intervention increased and was now felt in different aspects of the state. However, the Maharaja was still supreme authority in the state. The new Maharaja introduced a good number of reforms and improvements. He divided the administrative structure into various departments including Daftar Nizamat, Daftar Diwani and Daftar Jangi.⁷¹ New sub-divisions⁷² were created for both civil and revenue administration. The administration of justice was placed under the Nizamat department. Maharaja Ranbir Singh was anxious to improve the judicial system and now for the first time in the history of the state, a penal code was introduced. The said code was inspired as well as drawn upon the lines of Lord Macaulay's Indian Penal Code,⁷³ but contained only one hundred sections.⁷⁴ This code was published in bilingual treaties, in Dogri and Persian was known as Ranbir Dand Bidhi. The code with various amendments formed the nucleus of the laws and judicial processes operating in the state.

Convinced that the safety of our government in the colony depends upon the satisfaction and protection we are enabled to give to the natives of the country, the British started the limited intervention initially. From 1856, the GOI was exercising jurisdiction over European visitors to the state through the official known as officer-on-special-duty. In 1872, he was designated 'Political Agent' and 'Justice of Peace' and his main duty was to look after the interests of European visitors in the state.⁷⁵ He was entrusted by the British to exercise first class magisterial powers in respect of civil and criminal cases involving Europeans and the subjects of the Maharaja.⁷⁶

A remarkable change was witnessed when a high court, with defined powers, was established in the state in 1877. It was known as Adalat-i-Alia and deemed for the purpose of all enactments for

⁶⁹ *Horse-lifters*, those mostly come from Muzaffarabad during Dogra period.

⁷⁰ The number of village officials were not only punished if they failed in their services but also rewarded for aiding the state in suppressing the crime. (various adm reports)

⁷¹ G. L. Kaul, *Kashmir Through the Ages*, (Srinagar: Chronicle Publishing House, 1963), p. 103

⁷² P. N. K. Bamzai, *A History of Kashmir*, (Delhi: Metropolitan, 1962), p. 667

⁷³ P.N.K. Bamzai, *A History of Kashmir*, p. 667

⁷⁴ G.L. Koul, *Kashmir Through the Ages*, p. 103

⁷⁵ Foreign (Secret), Report October 1872, nos. 377, NAI

⁷⁶ S. C. Bajpai, *The Northern Frontier of India*, (Calcutta: Allied Publishers Pvt. Ltd., 1970), p. 84

the time being in force to be the highest court of appeal or revision, subject to the control and the judicial powers exercised by His Highness the Maharaja. The general superintendence and control over all other civil courts shall be vested in, and all such courts shall be subordinate to the high court.⁷⁷ At the same time the rules for court fee, stamp duties and registration were also framed.⁷⁸ By 1885, Sadar Adalats had been established both at Jammu and Srinagar. The judges of these Adalats were subordinate to the Governors of their respective provinces, whose advice were sought while deciding important cases. At the same, the powers of the courts were confined to civil and criminal cases only, the revenue cases were decided by the Governor. They also inspected the work of the village headmen, who served in detecting and reporting crime. There were different types of courts in the state such as courts of tehsildars, courts of wazirs or district officers, city courts etc.⁷⁹ In total there were twenty-five courts of law in the state during the time of Ranbir Singh, of which fourteen were wazarat courts, situated at Srinagar, Anantnag, Haripur, Kamraj, Reasi, Nowshara, Kishtwar and Bhaderwah.⁸⁰ There were also three courts one each at Ladakh, Gilgit, and Skardu. Besides, there was a court at Srinagar called Adalat-Dag-i-Shawl. New court room, record offices⁸¹ and prison houses had also been established in the state by this time.

The Maharajas personal interest and participation in all endeavours for establishing a systematic administration and improvising law and order conditions were successful to a large extent. But it is equally true that the aim of impartial judicial system was not materialised. It is clear that the Maharajas aim of dispensing true and speedy justice was not achieved, primarily owing to the absence of trained persons and uniform laws and procedures.⁸² One hundred sections of criminal law and a simple code of civil laws were not sufficient to meet the requirements of the people. The system remained more or less medieval as the administration of both civil and criminal justice in the state was more or less a farce.⁸³ The judiciary from the inception of the treaty to the deposition of the Maharaja (1889) witnessed a unique era of transformation. The introduction of the Ranbir Dand Bidhi, the establishment of mixed court, Adalat-i-Alia, establishment of other courts and there was also beginning of court fee, stamps , supervision of jails and appointment of judges. Despite of all these developments the judicial administration still remained in practice arbitrary, mixed and even brutal. It was only after the direct colonial intervention the judicial system of the State was finally reorganised on British lines from last decade of the nineteenth century.

⁷⁷ G L Kaul, *Kashmir Through the Ages*, p. 105

⁷⁸ Nar Singh Das Narain, *Tarikh-i-Dogra Desh*, Urdu(Jammu: Chand Publishing House,1967),pp. 667-68

⁷⁹ Charles Bates, *A Gazetteer of Kashmir*,(Srinagar: Gulshan Books, 2005), p. 96

⁸⁰ Nar Singh Das Narain, *Tarikh-i-Dogra Desh*, (Urdu), pp. 667-668

⁸¹ G.M.D. Sufi, *Kashmir: Being a history From Earliest Times to Our Own*, p. 797

⁸² There was a penal code, but no code of criminal procedure. Similarly, there was a code of civil procedure, but there was no substantive code of civil law, nor any law of limitation.

⁸³ From Col. Nisbat to Secretary GOI, dated February 1891, nos. 295-326, NAI